

Direct ink writing of recycled magnesite refractories from ladle metallurgy waste

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ABSTRACT

Refractory linings in ladle metallurgy are heat-resistant materials that protect ladles from high temperatures and aggressive chemicals during metal processing. They must withstand mechanical wear, chemical corrosion, and thermal shocks. The most common lining materials are MgO and CaO bricks, known for their high temperature resistance and good durability against both acidic and basic slags. This process generates significant amounts of waste due to wear and spalling during operation. While some by-products are already being reused, a large portion is still landfilled. This study focuses on the development of a new type of refractory material produced using direct ink writing. For this purpose, MgO refractory waste (MGW) was mixed with either B1M or IBV kaolins. A total of 12 mixtures with the addition of 50, 60, 70, 80, and 90 wt% MGW were prepared. All materials were characterized using chemical, phase, granulometric, and scanning electron microscopy analyses. Rheological properties of the mixtures were studied. For each sample, two firing temperatures (1000 °C and 1200 °C) were tested. Compressive strength, bulk density, apparent porosity, and water absorption of the fired samples were evaluated.

1. Introduction

Refractory ceramics, defined as non-metallic material with suitable chemical and physical properties for use in structures or systems exposed to temperatures above 538 °C [1,2], play an important role in high-temperature industrial processes. Most thermal units, such as those used in steel processing, are composed of a permanent lining and a working lining, supplemented by an insulating layer and a steel shell [3,4]. Refractory linings in industrial furnaces serve multiple functions – protective, containment, and thermal insulation – enabling safe and efficient operation at extreme temperatures. The typical service temperature varies depending on the application, e.g. ~1450 °C for steel ladles, ~1500 °C during iron melting, and up to 2000 °C in some cement kiln operations. This broad temperature applicability underscores the

versatility and critical importance of refractory ceramics in industrial production, especially in metallurgical processes having the largest consumption (~60 %) of these materials [4–7]. Steel and blast furnace slag production closely follows global steel and iron output. In 2024, total world crude steel production was nearly 1.9·10⁹ tons (Gt) (2.5·10⁶ tons in Czech Republic) [8] and the steel slag output exceeded 120·10⁶ tons [9].

Although the refractory materials represent a heterogeneous group, oxide refractories are the most widely used in metallurgy. The main types are magnesia (MgO, MgO-C, MgO-Al₂O₃), lime/dolomite (CaO, (Ca,Mg)O), or silica (SiO₂) refractories, and spinel or chromite systems (MgAl₂O₄, MgCr₂O₄) combined with carbon phases (C). The current trend, however, is to increase sustainability by replacing these primary raw materials with wastes. It is possible to reuse the waste linings from

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steelmaking technologies [10,11]. A key issue is the spontaneous hydration of free CaO when exposed to moisture, forming Ca(OH)₂. This leads to ~200 % volume expansion, causing cracking and disintegration, which complicates their production, storage, and use [12–15].

In addition to the use of non-magnesium wastes as additives to MgO-C refractories (e.g. TiB₂-BN-AlN [16,17]), many authors reported MgO-containing wastes directly as an alternative raw materials suitable for the preparation of CaO-MgO-SiO₂ insulating refractories [18], magnesium oxychloride cement composites [19], Mg-Zr refractories [20], MgO-C refractories [21], or cordierite ceramics [22], to name a few. The alternative raw material studied is usually MgO-C waste [19–22], but waste phosphorus tailings rich in MgO were also reported [18]. A common element of these studies is the traditional preparation method, either (isostatic) pressing [18,20–24] or mold casting [19,25], and to our knowledge, the processing of MgO refractory waste using the Direct Ink Writing (DIW) has not been published yet.

The DIW is an additive manufacturing technique enabling a layer-by-layer fabrication of 3D structures through the controlled extrusion of viscoplastic inks or pastes [26–28]. One of the most significant advantages of DIW is the ability to process a wide range of materials, not only ceramics, polymers, metals and composites, but also recycled or waste raw materials, provided that these materials are formulated into pastes or slurries with suitable rheological properties such as shear-thinning (pseudoplastic) behavior and stable yield stress [29–32]. Additionally, while other 3D printing methods often require support structures or high-temperature processing, DIW can operate under ambient conditions and, given the appropriate rheological properties of the material, does not require any scaffolding [29]. The shear-thinning behavior is crucial for DIW, as it enables easy extrusion by reducing viscosity with increasing shear stress [33]. The values of G' (storage modulus) and G'' (loss modulus) play an important role — their equality indicates the onset of flow. Inappropriate shear stress can lead to either difficult extrusion (too high) or spontaneous flow (too low) [34,35].

The possibility of processing refractory MgO waste using DIW would be very useful for sustainability and the circular economy. This is our motivation. This study has three research objectives: (1) to confirm or refute the possibility of using the DIW method for mixtures of kaolin with different amounts of MgO refractory waste, (2) to evaluate the behavior of the tested mixtures during DIW, and (3) to analyze the final properties of the printed samples after firing at 1000 °C and 1200 °C. For this purpose, two different kaolins were studied, each original and also in a mixture with five different amounts of MgO refractory waste (50–90 wt%). Detailed rheological measurements were performed. Four main properties (compressive strength, bulk density, apparent porosity, and water absorption) of each sample were determined. The research also includes chemical, phase, granulometric, and scanning electron microscopy analyses of the materials.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

The MgO refractory waste (MGW) was obtained from Trinecké železářny Inc., Czech Republic (Fig. 1). This material can be characterized as a waste product/material generated during the replacement of lining materials in steelmaking furnaces. Both clays (kaolins) B1M and IBV were supplied by LB MINERALS, s.r.o, Czech Republic. The IBV kaolin comes from the “Novoves layer” at Nová Ves quarry (50.1776908N, 12.4081744E). The refractoriness is 1730–1760 °C, with a sintering temperature >1450 °C. Drying shrinkage of IBV is ~3–5 % [35]. The B1M kaolin comes from “Vonšov layers” at Nová Ves quarry. The refractoriness is 1700–1740 °C, with a sintering temperature of 1050–1100 °C. Drying shrinkage of B1M is ~6–8 % [35].

Fig. 1. Original form of the MgO refractory waste (MGW) from lining.

2.2. Preparation of mixtures

While fine-grained kaolins B1M and IBV were used without pre-treatment, the MGW was milled and sieved to below 1.0 mm. For the experiment, MGW was mixed with either B1M or IBV kaolin in five following kaolin:MGW mass ratios: 50:50, 40:60, 30:70, 20:80, and 10:90. Three variables affect DIW: (1) kaolin:MGW mass ratio, (2) amount of water added, and (3) 3D printer settings (DIW conditions). Adding the same amount of water for each kaolin:MGW mass ratio would mean changing the DIW conditions every time due to the different rheological behavior of the resulting mixtures, i.e. not every such mixture would be printable under the same DIW conditions [35]. In this study, the same DIW conditions were used for each mixture (see section 2.3). Therefore, it was necessary to adjust the amount of water for each kaolin:MGW mass ratio (Table S1) to achieve the optimal consistency for the DIW process. The adjustment of water content for various mixtures with different composition of solids was already reported [36–39]. The addition of water in this study was based on our previous practical experiences [35].

2.3. DIW conditions

Test samples (Fig. 2) were prepared from all ten mixtures and two pure kaolins using Moore 2 Ceramic & Clay 3D printer (Tronxy, Shenzhen, China). A grid infill pattern was chosen for printing (Fig. S1). The reasons for this choice are lower material consumption while maintaining high strength, as well as more uniform possible deformation of the printed object [40]. Material was pushed by a screw conveyor through a 2.5 mm nozzle onto the print bed. The bottom and top layers of the printed models were 1 mm high, with intermediate layers at 1.3 mm. Printing speeds were 20 mm s⁻¹ for top and bottom layers and 40 mm s⁻¹ for intermediate layers. Each print line was 2 mm wide.

Size of each test sample was 2 × 2 × 2 cm. The printing was followed by a continuous drying at 110 °C until constant weight was reached (24 h). Printed bodies were then fired in electric laboratory kiln at 1000 °C and 1200 °C for 5 h.

2.4. Characterization and evaluation methods

Chemical composition was analyzed by energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRFS) method using SPECTRO XEPOS spectrometer (Spectro Analytical Instruments, Kleve, Germany). Phase composition was analyzed by X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) analysis using X-ray diffractometer SUPERMINI 200 (Rigaku, Japan) equipped with Co lamp ($\lambda = 1.7889 \text{ \AA}$) and D/teX Ultra detector. XRPD patterns were recorded in 5–90° 2 θ range (scanning rate of 5° · min⁻¹). ICDD PDF 2 release 2014 database was used to determine the phase composition.

Fig. 2. The appearance of printed and dried samples of pure kaolins (B1M, IBV), and mixtures containing 50, 60, 70, 80, or 90 wt % of MGW.

Particle size distribution (PSD) was analyzed using Mastersizer 3000+ Ultra (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., Malvern, UK) by Aero method for the range of 0.01–3500 μm . Morphology was analyzed by scanning electron microscopy using SEM/EDAX QUANTA 650 FEG microscope (FEI, Hillsboro, USA) with backscattered electron detector. Samples were attached to carbon tape on an Al stub and were not sputtered. The analysis was carried out under vacuum (~ 50 Pa). Acceleration voltage of 20 kV was used.

Rheological properties of raw mixtures were measured using a Thermo Haake MARS iQ Air rotational rheometer at 23 °C using roughened parallel plates (\varnothing 25 mm, gap = 5 mm). Shear-thinning behavior was determined using Rotation Ramp measurements in Control Rate mode, with a shear rate range from $4 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ up to the point of failure.

The resulting data were fitted using the Power Law model, where parameter a represents the scale factor, b is the power exponent, and r is the correlation coefficient indicating the goodness of fit. Using the Oscillatory Amplitude Sweep test ($f = 1$ Hz, τ from 1 Pa up to failure), the storage modulus G' and the loss modulus G'' were determined, which allowed the changes in the viscoelastic properties of the material to be monitored. From the test, it was also possible to identify the boundary of the linear viscoelastic region and the critical cross point $G' = G''$ where the transition from elastic to viscous behavior occurs.

Bulk density, water adsorption, apparent porosity, and compressive strength of the fired samples were determined from 5 samples each.

Bulk density, water absorption, and apparent porosity were determined gravimetrically according to standards ČSN EN 771-1 and EN 72 2603. Weighing of samples was performed on hydrostatically balanced scales. The following procedure was used. Each dry sample was weighed to obtain the mass of dry sample (m_1). The dry samples were then placed in a container of distilled water. No sample touched another sample or the walls of the container, and all samples were completely submerged. The water was brought to a boil, the boil was maintained for 2 h, and during this time more distilled water was added as needed so that the samples remained completely submerged (at least 20 mm below the water surface). After 2 h of boiling, the samples were allowed to cool. Each sample was then weighed in distilled water to obtain the mass of water-saturated sample in water (m_3). Finally, each sample was removed from the water, surface of the sample was wiped with a damp cloth, and the sample was weighed to obtain the mass of the water-saturated sample in air (m_2).

Bulk density (BD; $\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$), indicating the mass per unit volume of the sample, including voids and pores, was calculated using the equation

$$\text{BD} = \rho \cdot (m_1 / (m_2 - m_3)) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where ρ is a density of distilled water ($\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$), m_1 (g) is mass of dry sample, m_2 (g) is mass of the water-saturated sample in air, and m_3 (g) is

mass of water-saturated sample in water.

Water absorption (WA; in %) was calculated using the equation

$$\text{WA} = 100 \cdot (m_2 - m_1) / m_1 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where m_1 (g) is mass of dry sample, and m_2 (g) is mass of the water-saturated sample in air,.

Apparent porosity (AP), i.e. the ratio of the volume of open pores and voids in a sample to its total volume, including all pores and voids, was calculated using the equation

$$\text{AP} = 100 \cdot (m_2 - m_1) / (m_2 - m_3) \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

where m_1 (g) is mass of dry sample, m_2 (g) is mass of the water-saturated sample in air, and m_3 (g) is mass of water-saturated sample in water.

Compressive strength (CS) was determined according to standards ČSN EN 772-1 and EN 772-605. The following procedure was used. Each sample was placed on the lower pressure plate of a hydraulic press LLB1 (Brio Hranice s.r.o., Czech Republic). The upper pressure plate of the press was then brought closer to the sample so that the plate was in contact with the entire upper side of the sample. A continuously increasing compressive load was then applied to the sample. The load increase was stopped when the sample fractured. The CS (in MPa) was calculated using the equation

$$\text{CS} = F / S \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

where F (N) is the highest load at failure of the whole samples and S (mm^2) is a compression area calculated from the sample dimensions. For the average values of the dimensions of samples, the reader is referred to Table S2.

2.5. Chemical and phase analyses of MGW and kaolins

XRFS analysis (Table 1) confirmed that MGW is a $\text{MgO-CaO-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ system with a dominant MgO and CaO

Table 1
Composition (in wt.%) of MgO refractory waste (MGW) and each kaolin (B1M and IBV) according to XRFS analysis.

oxides	MGW	B1M	IBV	oxides	MGW	B1M	IBV
Na_2O	0.15	0.12	0.15	TiO_2	0.37	0.85	1.22
MgO	26.27	0.38	0.29	ZrO_2	0.26	–	–
Al_2O_3	7.16	35.64	36.10	P_2O_5	0.40	–	–
SiO_2	11.64	45.52	45.50	Cr_2O_3	1.71	–	–
Fe_2O_3	10.68	3.02	1.95	MnO	1.84	–	–
K_2O	0.29	2.94	3.68	NiO	0.03	–	–
CaO	28.77	0.35	0.23	LOI	9.67	10.92	10.55
SO_3	0.68	–	–				

content (>26 wt% each). Amount of SiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ is ~2.5 times lower, the amount of Al₂O₃ is ~4.0 times lower.

Amounts of the main components of B1M and IBV (~45.5 wt% SiO₂ and ~36 wt% Al₂O₃; Table 1) indicate the high purity of these kaolins – note that an ideal kaolinite with crystallochemical formula Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄ contains ~46.6 wt% SiO₂ and ~39.5 wt% Al₂O₃. Minor oxides in B1M and IBV are mainly K₂O and Fe₂O₃, with B1M containing more Fe₂O₃ (~3 wt%) and IBV containing more K₂O (~3.7 wt%).

XRPD analysis of MGW (Fig. 3a) revealed a relatively diverse phase composition with the most intense reflections of periclase followed by calcium silicate and eight other phases. The composition of the identified phases (Fig. 3a) corresponds well with the composition of MGW according to XRF analysis (Table 1). XRPD patterns of both kaolins B1M (Fig. 3b) and IBV (Fig. 3c) showed that these kaolins consist of kaolinite accompanied by illite/hydromuscovite, quartz, and traces of anatase. As in the case of MGW, the composition of the identified phases for the B1M and IBV kaolins is in good agreement with the composition according to XRF analysis (Table 1). The average amount of Al₂O₃, SiO₂, K₂O, and TiO₂ in both kaolins is 36.4 wt%, 45.5 wt%, 3.3 wt%, and 1.0 wt%, respectively. If the kaolinite: illite (hydromuscovite): quartz:

anatase ratio is 30 : 4 : 5 : 1.5, then the amount of Al₂O₃, SiO₂, K₂O, and TiO₂ is 37.7 wt%, 47.1 wt%, 3.3 wt%, and 1.0 wt%, respectively. Despite neglecting some minor oxides present in the real kaolins (e.g. Fe₂O₃), this significant similarity of the calculated values with the average values obtained from Table 1 shows the dominance of kaolinite over the other phases.

2.6. Granulometry and morphology of MGW and kaolins

Particle size distribution of the input materials (Fig. 4) shows fine-grained nature of both kaolins compared to MGW, and also their mutual differences. While for B1M kaolin the values d₁₀ = 1.27 μm, d₅₀ = 3.88 μm, and d₉₀ = 12 μm were found, in the case of IBV kaolin the values are d₁₀ = 2.93 μm, d₅₀ = 15.9 μm, and d₉₀ = 95.3 μm, i.e. about two, four, and eight times higher, respectively. For milled and sieved MGW, the values d₁₀ = 8.86 μm, d₅₀ = 163 μm, and d₉₀ = 584 μm were found, with d₅₀ and d₉₀ being order of magnitude larger compared to kaolins. MGW particles thus serve as refractory aggregates. The smaller kaolin particles adhere to the MGW particles and provide the necessary cohesive and plastic properties of the kaolin:MGW mixtures.

Fig. 3. (a) XRPD diffractogram of MGW. 1 – periclase (MgO; PDF 00-045-0946), 2 – calcite (CaCO₃; PDF 01-083-4612), 3 – corundum (Al₂O₃; PDF 01-088-0826), 4 – forsterite (Mg₂SiO₄; PDF 01-071-1081), 5 – calcium silicate (Ca₃SiO₅; PDF 00-031-0301), 6 – magnesiochromite (MgCr₂O₄; PDF 01-071-3849), 7 – hausmanite (Mn₃O₄; PDF 01-080-0382), 8 – brownmillerite (Ca₂(FeAl_{0.9}Mg_{0.1})O₅; PDF 01-077-3908), 9 – wüstite (FeO; PDF 01-077-7981), and 10 – silicon oxide (SiO₂; PDF 00-043-0784). (b) XRPD diffractogram of B1M kaolin. 1 – kaolinite (Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄; PDF 00-001-0527), 2 – illite-hydromuscovite (KAl₃Si₃O₁₀(OH)₂; PDF 00-026-0911), 3 – quartz (SiO₂; PDF 01-086-2237), 4 – anatase (TiO₂; PDF 00-004-0477). (c) XRPD diffractogram of IBV kaolin. 1 – kaolinite (Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄; PDF 00-001-0527), 2 – hydromuscovite (KAl₃Si₃O₁₀(OH)₂; PDF 00-001-1098), 3 – quartz (SiO₂; PDF 01-086-2237), 4 – anatase (TiO₂; PDF 00-004-0477).

Fig. 4. Particle size distribution of kaolins (B1M, IBV) and MGW.

The difference in particle sizes (from the finest in B1M to the largest in MGW) is also visible in SEM images (Fig. 5). Moreover, morphological analysis revealed differences in shapes of the particles. While B1M (Fig. 5a) predominantly contains elongated, elliptical particles with higher eccentricity and lower compactness, indicating irregular, jagged particle outlines, particles in the IBV (Fig. 5b) exhibit slightly greater integrity and smoother contours, as reflected by a marginally higher solidity value. They are more flake-shaped than B1M kaolin. Particles in the MGW (Fig. 5c) show the highest compactness and the lowest average eccentricity, suggesting a predominance of rounded, nearly isotropic forms.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Rheological properties of mixtures

The rheological properties of the mixtures represent a key parameter influencing the success of the DIW process. The dependencies of shear rate on shear viscosity for all B1M:MGW and IBV:MGW mixtures, including their pure components, are presented in Fig. 6. The measurements were performed in the ramp test mode (Controlled Rate Mode), which characterizes the dynamic flow behavior. During the linear increase of shear rate, the material does not have sufficient time to relax its internal structure, and the measured data therefore correspond to the steady-flow regime. From a practical perspective, this is important because the DIW process operates at high shear rates, i.e., within the region of fully developed flow. All flow curves were well described by the Power Law model, confirming the pseudoplastic (shear-thinning)

behavior of the investigated pastes within the studied shear-rate range. For B1M-based mixtures (Fig. 6a), the B1M_80 sample exhibited the lowest viscosity and the lowest value of critical shear stress (τ_c), at which structural collapse occurred. A higher proportion of coarse MGW particles improved the spatial packing of the mixture (the so-called bimodal packing effect), thereby reducing the effective solid volume fraction and consequently the viscosity in the steady-shear region. At the same time, the lower water content limited plastic rearrangement between particles, resulting in a more brittle structure that failed more easily under shear loading. In contrast, B1M mixtures with a lower MGW content showed higher viscosity and higher critical shear stress (τ_c) values, indicating greater resistance to shear deformation and a more stable particle microstructure. A similar trend was observed for IBV-based mixtures (Fig. 6b). The pure IBV exhibited the highest viscosity, while the IBV_80 sample showed the lowest viscosity across the entire measured range. Samples IBV, IBV_60, and IBV_90 displayed higher critical shear stress (τ_c) values, suggesting that these mixtures can withstand greater mechanical loads before structural breakdown, and therefore exhibit higher stability under shear stress. It should be emphasised that the τ_c values listed in Table 2 do not represent a yield stress obtained from model fitting, but rather the maximum shear stress recorded immediately before structural collapse during the steady-shear test. While the IBV_80 mixture reached the minimum viscosity due to an optimal ratio of fine and coarse particles, where the fine IBV fraction effectively filled the voids between MGW particles, the IBV_90 mixture contained too few fine particles. As a result, the system behaved predominantly as a suspension composed of coarse MGW particles with a higher effective solid fraction and prevailing frictional contacts between

Fig. 5. SEM images of a) B1M, b) IBV, and c) MGW. Detailed structure at higher magnification is provided in the inset of each image.

Fig. 6. Power Law models from Shear rate vs. Shear viscosity measurements of a) B1M-based and b) IBV-based samples.

Table 2

Critical shear stress τ_c (Pa), viscosity at structural failure η_c (Pa·s), critical shear rate γ_c (s^{-1}) and dimensionless power law parameters a, b, r.

sample	τ_c	η_c	γ_c	a	b	r
B1M	2723	55940	0.04868	7474	-0.7183	0.9997
B1M_50	2378	42670	0.05574	3810	-0.8724	0.9999
B1M_60	1764	25580	0.06898	2668	-0.8689	0.9999
B1M_70	2038	30320	0.06721	3139	-0.8483	0.9999
B1M_80	1613	11260	0.1433	2324	-0.8341	0.9998
B1M_90	3031	36770	0.08242	5696	-0.7862	0.9993
IBV	2252	32490	0.06931	5051	-0.7489	0.9998
IBV_50	1696	11860	0.143	2047	-0.8703	0.9998
IBV_60	2405	14020	0.1715	3153	-0.8449	0.9999
IBV_70	1281	7429	0.1725	2361	-0.7785	0.9999
IBV_80	1179	14310	0.08237	2253	-0.7664	0.9997
IBV_90	2123	30780	0.06898	4094	-0.7857	0.9998

particles, which led to a renewed increase in both viscosity and τ_c .

The oscillatory rheological tests (Figs. 7 and 8, Table 3) complement the results of the steady-shear measurements and provide additional insight into the strength and cohesion of the particle network. For mixtures containing MGW, steeper shear rate–viscosity dependences were observed (Fig. 6), indicating more pronounced shear-thinning behavior, which can be advantageous for nozzle printability during the DIW process. Oscillatory measurements showed that the samples with MGW addition exhibited lower shear stress at the crossover point ($G' = G''$).

The presence of MGW tends to reduce the structural strength of the particle network under oscillation, leading to partial disruption of the system's internal cohesion during deformation. As in the previous test, the B1M_80 sample exhibited the lowest shear stress at the crossover point (Fig. 7), which can be attributed to a combination of lower water content, higher MGW fraction, and the specific ratio of the B1M, likely resulting in a more brittle and less cohesive structure. In contrast, the B1M_50 reached higher values of both the modulus at $G' = G''$ and the corresponding shear stress, indicating the presence of a stronger internal network. This sample also showed the highest shear stress at the end of the linear viscoelastic region (End of LVR), confirming its higher resistance to mechanical deformation. It can therefore be concluded that the addition of MGW can, in certain cases, have a positive effect on deformation strength, with the resulting influence depending on the mutual ratio of the individual components in the sample.

For the IBV-based samples (Fig. 8), the oscillatory rheological

measurements confirmed the trends observed in the viscosity tests. The highest shear stress at the crossover point ($G' = G''$) was recorded for the pure IBV, while MGW-containing samples showed a decreasing trend of this parameter. This indicates that the addition of MGW may reduce the shear strength of the structure during oscillatory deformation, thereby partially weakening the cohesion of the particle network. The results of both methods – steady-shear and oscillatory tests – were mutually consistent. Samples IBV, IBV_60, and IBV_90 exhibited the highest structural resistance to deformation, as reflected by both the crossover point values and the maximum shear stress at the end of the linear viscoelastic region (End of LVR). These mixtures withstood higher mechanical loads before structural failure, confirming their greater mechanical stability and stronger internal network arrangement. The rheological behavior of these mixtures therefore suggests their suitability for applications requiring enhanced resistance to mechanical stress. In contrast, the IBV_50 sample showed the highest G' and G'' moduli but reached the crossover point at the lowest shear stress among all investigated mixtures (Fig. 8). This phenomenon can be interpreted as a manifestation of structural brittleness, likely caused by the specific ratio of components in the mixture, which limited the plasticity of the particle network.

The rheological measurements confirmed that the addition of MGW significantly affects both the flow and mechanical properties of the mixtures. Samples containing MGW exhibited pronounced shear-thinning behavior, which is favourable for the DIW process; however, a higher MGW content combined with a lower water fraction led to a reduction in the structural integrity of the paste. Among the B1M-based samples, the B1M_50 showed the highest structural stability, whereas B1M_80 was the least resistant to shear loading. For the IBV-based samples, the highest mechanical stability was observed for IBV, IBV_60, and IBV_90, while the IBV_50 exhibited signs of structural weakening and reduced particle-network cohesion. Overall, it can be concluded that the influence of MGW on the rheological behavior of the mixtures is nonlinear and depends on the mutual ratio of the individual components. To achieve optimal properties, the composition must be carefully optimised with respect to the balance between fine and coarse fractions as well as the liquid-phase content.

3.2. Phase analysis of fired materials

XRPD analysis of samples fired at 1000 °C and 1200 °C (Fig. 9) showed periclase (MgO, PDF 00-045-0946) as the dominant component

Fig. 7. Oscillatory stress sweep results: Storage and Loss moduli (G' and G'') with cross points for B1M-based samples.

Fig. 8. Oscillatory stress sweep results: Storage and Loss moduli (G' and G'') with cross points for IBV-based samples.

Table 3

Crossover point $G' = G''$ (Pa), oscillatory stress at crossover points τ (Pa), shear rate at the end of linear viscoelastic region $\dot{\gamma}_{LVR}$ (s^{-1}), and oscillatory stress at the end of linear viscoelastic region τ_{LVR} (Pa) for each sample.

sample	$G' = G''$	τ	$\dot{\gamma}_{LVR}$	τ_{LVR}
IBV	2930	1640	0.0002369	290.1
IBV_50	9624	743.2	0.0002167	184.6
IBV_60	2662	1605	0.0002509	357.0
IBV_70	1983	771.2	0.0002339	199.2
IBV_80	8788	744.0	0.0002404	207.2
IBV_90	1381	1531	0.0002730	397.6
B1M	3674	2738	0.0002871	371.3
B1M_50	30180	2288	0.0008503	1006
B1M_60	20510	1323	0.0003189	345.9
B1M_70	3721	1540	0.0003904	425.6
B1M_80	7717	1034	0.0002444	243.2
B1M_90	3582	1644	0.0002465	367.3

(see the intensive reflections at ~ 50 and $\sim 74^\circ 2\theta$), confirming preservation of the basic refractory phase originating from MGW. Other identified phases included forsterite (Mg_2SiO_4 , PDF 01-071-1081) and akermanite ($Ca_2Mg(Si_2O_7)$, PDF 01-079-2425) formed through the interaction of MgO with SiO_2 and CaO. The increase in the intensity of ($\sim 37^\circ 2\theta$) and (~ 40 – $43^\circ 2\theta$) reflections of forsterite and akermanite,

respectively, with increasing amount of MGW is clearly evident (Fig. 9). The presence of mullite ($(Al_{2.5}Si_{1.5})O_{9.75}$, PDF 01-082-0037) and corundum (Al_2O_3 , PDF 01-088-0826) indicates active transformation of alumina-rich clay components. The samples also contain anorthite ($CaAl_2(SiO_4)_2$, PDF 00-002-0523), quartz (SiO_2 , PDF 01-089-1961), potassium aluminum silicate ($KAlSi_3O_8$, PDF 00-050-0436), and small amounts of magnetite (Fe_3O_4 , PDF 01-076-7166), likely originating from impurities.

For both IBV and B1M kaolins fired at temperatures of $1000^\circ C$ and $1200^\circ C$, reflections corresponding to mullite ($Al_{2.5}Si_{1.5}O_{9.75}$) and quartz (SiO_2) were identified; in addition, for the IBV clay at $1000^\circ C$, the phase dehydroxylated muscovite ($KAl_3Si_3O_{11}$) at position ($\sim 10^\circ 2\theta$). With decreasing kaolin content, the intensity of these reflections decreases, which also confirms the formation of additional phases with the increasing MgO ratio in the mixture. Forsterite (Mg_2SiO_4) and akermanite ($Ca_2MgSi_2O_7$) influence the properties of refractory materials in different ways. Forsterite contributes to higher refractoriness (stable up to about $1890^\circ C$) and resistance to basic corrosion. In contrast, akermanite has lower refractoriness (melting at approximately 1450 – $1500^\circ C$), which may limit the maximum operating temperature of refractories, but it positively affects their elasticity and resistance to thermal shock. Anorthite is formed at high temperatures

Fig. 9. XRPD diffractograms of pure IBV kaolin and IBV-based samples fired at $1000^\circ C$ (a) and $1200^\circ C$ (b), and of pure B1M kaolin and B1M-based samples fired at $1000^\circ C$ (c) and $1200^\circ C$ (d). 1 – dehydroxylated muscovite ($KAl_3Si_3O_{11}$; PDF No. 00-046-0741), 2 – quartz (SiO_2 ; PDF No. 01-089-1961), 3 – mullite ($Al_{2.5}Si_{1.5}O_{9.75}$; PDF No. 01-082-0037), 4 – forsterite high (Mg_2SiO_4 ; PDF No. 01-071-1081), 5 – potassium aluminum silicate ($KAlSi_3O_8$; PDF No. 00-050-0436), 6 – anorthite ($CaAl_2(SiO_4)_2$; PDF No. 00-002-0523), 7 – periclase (MgO ; PDF No. 00-045-0946), 8 – akermanite ($Ca_2Mg(SiO_7)$; PDF No. 01-079-2425), 9 – hematite (Fe_2O_3 ; PDF No. 01-084-9870).

(1000–1250 °C) by the reaction of CaO, Al₂O₃, and SiO₂.

3.3. Properties of fired materials

Visual observation of all samples fired at 1000 °C or 1200 °C (Fig. 10) revealed that the presence of MGW affects the volume and the firing temperature affects the color. The samples maintained their integrity, and no cracking or any other destruction was observed.

The internal structure based on the grid infill pattern used was also preserved. A very well-printable IBV_80 sample fired at either 1000 °C or 1200 °C and then broken is shown as an example (Fig. 11). The grid infill pattern is still visible for both temperatures (Fig. 11). These materials have an internal structure of interconnected voids (originating from the grid filling) and pores (in the fired mixture itself), which is related to the resulting porosity.

With two exceptions (B1M_90 and IBV_90 fired at 1000 °C and 1200 °C, respectively), the volume of the samples increased after firing (Table S3). The following three general relationships can be derived: the increase in volume was (a) higher at 1200 °C compared to 1000 °C, (b) higher for B1M-based samples compared to IBV-based samples, and (c) higher for samples with higher kaolin content.

Compressive strength tests and determination of bulk density, apparent porosity, and water absorption were performed on these fired samples (Figs. 12–15, Table S4).

The compressive strength values (Fig. 12, Table S4) show a positive effect of higher firing temperature for all samples. The effect of MGW can also be considered the same for both B1M and IBV-based samples: the more MGW, the lower the compressive strength. The type of kaolin in the mixture seems to be a key factor, as B1M-based samples exhibit higher compressive strength compared to IBV-based samples (the only exception is IBV_50 fired at 1200 °C). However, the compressive strength of pure IBV is higher compared to B1M at both firing temperatures.

The apparent porosity values (Fig. 13, Table S4) of MGW mixtures with kaolins are not significantly affected by the firing temperature. For B1M:MGW and IBV:MGW mixtures, the average difference is $4 \pm 3 \%$

and $2 \pm 1 \%$. Higher firing temperature led to lower apparent porosity for all IBV:MGW samples. However, B1M:MGW samples exhibit an increase in two cases (B1M_50 and B1M_90) and no change in one case (B1M_80). This different behavior, together with the fact that apparent porosity of B1M:MGW samples is slightly lower, can be explained by the smaller particle size of B1M compared to IBV (Fig. 4). This is also reflected in the porosity of pure B1M compared to pure IBV. The varying amounts of water added to the original mixtures may also play a role in the porosity values (Table S1).

The bulk density values (Fig. 14, Table S4) correlate with the apparent porosity values (Fig. 13, Table S4) – the lower the bulk density, the higher the apparent porosity and vice versa. As in the case of apparent porosity, the differences between the bulk densities of mixtures containing B1M or IBV are due to the difference in particle size of these kaolins (Fig. 5). In both mixtures, the highest densities are achieved by samples containing 70 wt% MGW (i.e. B1M_70 and IBV_70) and fired at 1200 °C. These samples also show the highest increase in bulk density with increasing firing temperature, which explains their highest increase in compressive strength (see Fig. 12). The pure kaolins exhibit approximately the same (IBV) or slightly higher (B1M) bulk density compared to these samples.

Water absorption (Fig. 15, Table S4) also correlates with apparent porosity (Fig. 13) and bulk density (Fig. 14) – the lower the absorption, the higher the density and the lower the porosity and vice versa. This is related to the higher water absorption of IBV-based samples compared to B1M-based samples, for both firing temperatures. Considering the results of previous analyses, it is not surprising that B1M_70 and IBV_70 samples show a significant decrease in water absorption after firing at 1200 °C. The increase in water absorption of sample B1M_50 fired at 1200 °C agrees with the changes in bulk density and apparent porosity observed for this sample, despite its high compressive strength. This can be explained by incomplete phase evolution or thermal instability.

4. Conclusions

The effect of the MGW:kaolin (either B1M or IBV) mass ratio on both

Fig. 10. The appearance of samples after firing at 1000 °C and 1200 °C.

Fig. 11. Sample IBV_80 fired at a) 1000 °C and b) 1200 °C.

Fig. 12. Compressive strength for all samples and both firing temperatures.

Fig. 13. Apparent porosity for all samples and both firing temperatures.

the printability of the tested mixtures and the properties of the materials after firing was studied and the key findings can be summarized in the seven following points.

- The MGW can be successfully used in a mixture with kaolin for DIW method.
- MGW-based insulating refractory materials useable at temperatures up to 1200 °C can be prepared using the DIW. Opening up new possibilities for the further use of MGW, this important finding is positive for sustainability and useful for the circular economy.
- Mixtures containing 50–80 wt% MGW exhibit very good printability, while mixtures with 90 wt% MGW start to suffer from water separation and rapid solidification during prolonged printing, which complicates the DIW.
- The addition of MGW stabilizes volume changes during firing – while the shrinkage of pure kaolins is up to 37 % at 1200 °C, volume

changes of mixtures containing 80–90 wt% MGW is <3.5 %, regardless of the kaolin type.

- The apparent porosity of all samples prepared from mixtures of MGW with kaolin and fired at 1200 °C reached ≥ 44 %.
- Although the highest compressive strength was achieved for 50 wt% MGW (up to 23.7 MPa in the case of B1M_50), the optimal compromise in terms of processability, stability and all properties is 80 wt% MGW.
- In terms of average values, the use of kaolin B1M with lower particle size resulted in lower apparent porosity (at both 1000 and 1200 °C), lower water absorption (at 1000 °C) and higher compressive strength (at both 1000 and 1200 °C) of the resulting fired materials. However, with respect to standard deviations, there is no significant difference between using B1M or IBV.

In the field of practical application, DIW of MGW mixtures with kaolin has significant potential, especially for the production of complex

Fig. 14. Bulk density for all samples and both firing temperatures. The numerical values are rounded to one decimal place. For unrounded values, the reader is referred to Table S4.

Fig. 15. Water absorption for all samples and both firing temperatures.

shaped insulating refractory components with controlled geometry. Improved insulation properties can also be expected due to the grid infill pattern used, which can result in slower heat conduction.

Further research will be focused on this topic and the corrosion resistance of the materials prepared in this study. Selected MGW-containing materials with the lowest heat conduction and the highest corrosion resistance can then be used in metallurgy and energy industry.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hana Ovčáčková: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Michaela Topinková:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jiří Fiedor:** Formal analysis. **Jonáš Tokarský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis. **Jiří Rozbroj:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **David Žurovec:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jakub Hlosta:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Radek Nikel:** Formal analysis. **Piotr Zubek:** Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2025.12.328>.

Data availability

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